

Separation of Technetium (VII) from other Elements by Extraction with Nitrobenzene Solution of Rhodamine-B Hydrochloride

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The extraction of technetium (VII) with rhodamine-B hydrochloride into organic solvents has been investigated. Nitrobenzene, which is the most effective extractant for Tc(VII) is used to separate Tc(VII) from other elements. It has been found that Tc(VII) is extracted as ion pairs.

SALTS of rhodamine-B have been used to extract a large number of halo-anions of metals such as Sb(V), Ga(III), Pd(II), Au(III), W(VI), Tl(III) and Re(VII)¹⁻⁷. However, the extraction of Tc(VII) has not been reported in the literature. The present work describes a rapid and selective method for the extraction of Tc(VII) with rhodamine-B hydrochloride into nitrobenzene and its application in the separation of Tc(VII) from other elements.

Experimental

Chemicals and Apparatus: All the chemicals, reagents and solvents used were of A.R. grade. Reagent grade (99% purity) rhodamine-B hydrochloride (RH⁺Cl⁻) of B.D.H. make was used in the extraction studies. Carrier solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate salts in double distilled water. Radio-isotopes were supplied by the Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay.

Preparation of pure Tc^{99m}: Tc^{99m} was obtained by irradiating spec pure molybdenum trioxide in the CIRUS reactor of the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, at a thermal neutron flux of 2×10^{12} n/cm²/sec. for one week. The Mo⁹⁹ produced by the n, γ reaction on stable Mo⁹⁸ decays to the 6 hr. Tc^{99m}. The Tc^{99m} was separated from parent Mo⁹⁹ by the method employed by Gerlit⁸. The radiochemical purity of the sample was checked by measuring the gamma spectra and following the half-life of the sample.

Procedure

1 ml of Tc^{99m} solution was taken in a 100 ml separatory funnel. 1 ml of 0.005% RH⁺Cl⁻ solution in alcohol was added. The pH of the solution was adjusted with HCl or NaOH keeping the total volume to 10 ml. 10 ml of nitrobenzene was added and the mixture was equilibrated for 2 min. In some experiments alcoholic solution of RH⁺Cl⁻ was not added to the aqueous phase. The aqueous phase

after adjustment of pH was equilibrated with 10 ml of nitrobenzene containing 0.005% of RH⁺Cl⁻. The two phases (10 ml each) were allowed to separate. Each phase was centrifuged and an aliquot of each phase was taken for counting. The pH of the equilibrated aqueous phase was recorded. The extraction of other ions was followed by using radioactive isotopes as tracers. Gamma-emitting samples were counted on a 1½" × 1½" well type NaI (TI) crystal in conjunction with a single channel pulse-height analyser. Beta-emitting isotopes were counted on an end window type G.M. counter after evaporating the solution to dryness. A 13.5 mg/cm² of Al absorber was interposed to cut off the soft conversion electrons of Tc^{99m}.

Results and Discussion

The extraction (Table 1) of Tc(VII) into nitrobenzene solution of RH⁺Cl⁻ is better than 99% over the pH range 2.7-6.0. The extraction equilibrium

TABLE I—EXTRACTION COEFFICIENT OF Tc(VII) BETWEEN NITROBENZENE (CONTAINING RH⁺Cl⁻) AN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

Volume of organic phase = 10 ml containing 5 mg. of RH⁺Cl⁻
Volume of aqueous phase = 10 ml.
Temperature = 28° ± 1°.

pH	Extraction coefficient* (E)	% Extraction
2.7	1466	99.93
3.7	2810	99.96
4.0	3800	99.97
4.5	5369	99.98
4.7	7961	99.98
5.2	5269	99.98
6.0	1620	99.98
6.7	0.237	19.15
8.8	0.031	3.01

* An average of at least two determinations. The variation of each value is within ±5% of the average value.

is reached within 2 min. and the separation of the two phases is rapid.

Table 2 illustrates that the extraction coefficient of Tc(VII) between an aqueous alcoholic solution of pH 4.7 containing RH^+Cl^- and organic solvent

TABLE 2—EXTRACTION COEFFICIENT OF Tc(VII) BETWEEN AN ORGANIC SOLVENT AND AQUEOUS ALCOHOLIC SOLUTION OF RH^+Cl^-

Volume of organic phase = 10 ml.
Aqueous alcoholic phase = 10 ml. of aqueous solution, containing 5 mg. of RH^+Cl^- in alcohol.
pH = 4.7. Temperature = $28^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Solvent	Extraction coefficient*	% Extraction
Nitrobenzene	5136	99.98
Quinoline	778	99.87
1,2-Dichloroethane	592.6	99.83
<i>o</i> -Dichlorobenzene	43.0	97.72
Ethyl acetate	28.0	96.55
<i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol	16.3	94.22
<i>iso</i> -Amyl alcohol	12.7	92.70
Ethyl methyl ketone	11.8	92.18
Chloroform	6.0	85.71
Amyl acetate	0.94	48.45
<i>n</i> -Butanol	0.10	9.09
Benzene	0.08	7.46
Xylene	0.034	3.29
Carbon tetrachloride	0.001	1.14

* An average of at least two determinations. The variation of each value is within $\pm 5\%$ of the average value.

decreases in the series :

Nitrobenzene > Quinoline > 1,2,-dichloroethane > *o*-Dichlorobenzene > Ethyl acetate > *n*-Amyl alcohol > *iso*-Amyl alcohol > Ethyl methyl ketone > Chloroform > Amyl acetate > *n*-Butanol > Xylene > Carbon tetrachloride. The results in Table 3 indicate that the extraction coefficient of Tc(VII) is lowered by the presence of anions investigated. However, it is greater than 160, except when ClO_4^- , IO_3^- , SCN^- and I^- are present.

Extraction studies with various elements show that the extraction of Ag(I), Hg(II), Mo(VI), Pt(V) are 13% or more. W(VI), Zr(IV), Au(III) and P(V) are extracted to the extent of 2.91%, 5.50%, 6.03% and 2.64% respectively. The extractions of Hg(II) and Ag(I) are reduced to 2.19% and 1.02% respectively by carrying out the extraction in the presence of sodium sulphide and thiosulphate. Sodium thiosulphate also lowers the extraction of Au(III) to 0.7% and Pt(IV) to 2.2%. However, 100 mg of sodium thiosulphate in 10 ml decreases the E value of Tc(VII) from 7961 to 223. Sodium fluoride decreases the extraction of Mo(VI) to 0.4%. The values of the separation factor (defined as the ratio of the extraction coefficient of Tc(VII) to that of the element of interest) for a number of elements are reported in Table 4.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SALTS ON THE EXTRACTION COEFFICIENT OF TECHNETIUM (VII)

Organic phase = 10 ml nitrobenzene containing 5 mg of RH^+Cl^- .
Aqueous phase = 10 ml aqueous acid phase of pH 4.7.
Temperature = $28^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Salt added	Conc. in molarity	Extraction coefficient* of Tc(VII)
Potassium sulphate	0.011	2548
Potassium oxalate	0.014	1902
Sodium potassium tartarate	0.007	1738
Potassium bromate	0.012	1379
Potassium persulphate	0.015	1141
Sodium sulphate	0.016	932
Sodium citrate	0.007	334
Sodium nitrate	0.023	336
Potassium bromide	0.017	301
Disodium EDTA	0.007	240
Sodium thiosulphate	0.008	223
Sodium nitrite	0.029	161
Potassium perchlorate	0.163	81
Potassium iodate	0.008	81
Potassium iodide	0.012	3.6
Potassium sulphocyanide	0.025	15.4

* An average of at least two determinations. The variation of each value is within $\pm 5\%$ of the average value.

TABLE 4—SEPARATION FACTORS FOR VARIOUS ELEMENTS

Organic phase = 10 ml of nitrobenzene containing 5 mg. of RH^+Cl^- .
Aqueous phase = 10 ml of aqueous phase of pH 4.7.
Temperature = $28^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Separation factor greater than	Elements
10^7	Ni(II), Mn(II), Mn(II) ^a , Zn(II), Sn(IV) ^b , Sb(III), Sb(III) ^a .
10^6	Zn(II), Zn(II) ^a , Cu(II), Cu(II) ^a , Co(II), Co(II) ^a , Ir(IV), Sc(III), Sc(III) ^a , Ti(II), Ca(II), Ca(II) ^a , W(VI), Ag(I) ^b , Mo(VI) ^c , Sn(IV) ^a , Cs(I), La(III), La(III) ^a , Au(III) ^b , Cr(III) ^a .
10^5	W(VI) ^a , Hg(II) ^a , Cd(II), Cd(II) ^a , Au(III), Pt(IV) ^b , Cr(III), Cr(VI) ^a .
10^4	Hg(II), Ag(I), Au(III) ^a .
10^3	Mo(VI) ^a , Cr(VI).
1.0	Pt(IV).

^a = with mg amounts of carrier

Masking agent added :

^b = $Na_2S_2O_3$

^c = NaF and ^d = Na_2S .

8–20 mg of the elements marked 'a' in Table 4 do not lower the E value of Tc(VII). However, Mo(VI), Cr(VI), Sn(II), and W(VI), reduce the E value of Tc(VII) to 30.10, 64.46, 0.505 and 7.5 respectively. The interference by W(VI) and Mo(VI) is negligible, if the extraction is carried out in the presence of 500 mg of NaF. Cr(VI) does not interfere when it is

reduced to Cr(III) with H_2O_2 in acid medium. The interference of Sn(II) becomes negligible when it is oxidised to Sn(IV).

The separation of carrier free Tc(VII) from each of the following milligram amounts of elements Zn(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Cr(III), Sb(III), Zr(IV), W(VI), Ca(II), P(V), Ag(I), Sc(III), Hg(II), La(III), Cd(II), Sn(IV) and Au(III) is achieved by extracting Tc(VII) into 10 ml of nitrobenzene containing 5 mg of RH^+Cl^- from an aqueous acid phase of pH 4.7 and washing the organic phase with 10 ml of acid solution of pH 4.7. Tc(VII) was reextracted into the aqueous phase by equilibrating the organic phase with 10 ml of 0.0271N NaOH. In the presence of NaF the same procedure permitted to separate Tc(VII) from 4.16 mg of Mo(VI), which was irradiated for one day at a flux of 2×10^{12} n/cm²/sec. The recovery of Tc(VII) is better than 99%. The total time required for the separation is found to be not more than 7 min.

Rhenium (VII) was found to follow Tc(VII) in the extraction and back extraction steps. Carrier free Tc(VII) was separated from μg quantities (ratio of activities 1:1) of Re(VII) by following the procedure given below :

The aqueous phase was evaporated almost to dryness. 2 ml of conc. HCl and 1 ml of hydrazine hydrate were added and the solution heated gently for 5-7 min. It was allowed to cool, made to pH 4.7 keeping the total volume to 10 ml and extracted with 10 ml of nitrobenzene containing RH^+Cl^- to remove rhenium. The aqueous phase containing technetium (IV) and traces of rhenium (VII) was again extracted with 10 ml of nitrobenzene containing RH^+Cl^- . An aliquot of the aqueous phase was checked for rhenium activity and its presence was found to be less than 1%. The yield of technetium was better than 98%.

The high extraction coefficient value of technetium (VII) between nitrobenzene solution of RH^+Cl^- and aqueous solution of pH 4.7 seems to suggest that

Tc(VII) is extracted as ion pairs. The extraction of Tc(VII) shows a first power dependence (Fig. 1) on the equilibrium concentration of RH^+Cl^- in nitrobenzene

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log[E]$ versus $\log[RH^+Cl^-]$. solvent—nitrobenzene. aqueous solution at pH—4.7.

(N.B.). The extraction process may be formulated as : $TcO_4^- + (RH^+Cl^-) \rightleftharpoons (RH^+TcO_4^-)_{NB} + Cl^-$. At chloride ion concentration of $7.2 \times 10^{-5}M$, the logarithm of the equilibrium constant is 3.56.

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